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Evaluation of Growth Performance and Nutrients Assimilation of Insect Feed in Nile Tilapia (*Oreochromis Niloticus*)

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾Aliza Saeed, Saima Naz ⁽²⁾Nadia Noureen*

⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾The Govt, Sadiq College Women University, Bahawalpur, Pakistan - *Corresponding Author Email: nadia.noureen@gscwu.edu.pk

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Abstract

the present study was planned to evaluate the effect of insect-based fish feed on the growth of Nile Tilapia. Blowfly larvae were collected, dried and grounded to get a powdered meal. Three diets were formulated with a 20 percent and 40 percent of larvae meal with conventional ingredients and a control diet with no maggot meal. The formulated diets were fed to fingerlings of Nile Tilapia in three different groups for ten weeks. All growth parameters, including weight, length, FCR, SGR and mortality rate, were observed throughout the study while physio-chemical parameters were kept at optimum ranges. The study revealed that the insect-based diet showed an efficient growth rate where the diet containing 40% maggot meal showed the highest weight and length gain. The growth rate for a diet containing 20% maggot meal and control diet was also good but FCR was highest in the group fed with diet having a 40% maggot meal. The least mortality rate was observed in maggot meal fed groups. The results indicated that feeds based on insects could provide the best alternative for expensive and unpalatable fish meals. However, it opens further needs of research in experimenting with different insect-based diets with different formulations to attain much better results.

Key Words: Insect Feed, Blow Fly, Tilapia, Growth Rate, FCR

INTRODUCTION

Culturing of Tilapia has been promoted in many countries like Thailand, Brazil, the Philippines and Malaysia with great demand in the global market. In 2010, in the United States which is the largest single market for Tilapia and global production of tilapia has reached 3.2 million tons (FAO, 2011). For intensive Tilapia culturing, a well-balanced fish feed is a primary need for fish. To fulfill this requirement, locally available and cheap ingredients can reduce cost effects. The challenge is to provide food that is highly nutritive and economically sustainable (Dada and Akinwande, 2005). Along with other conventional feeds, fish meal is being extensively used having high nutritional value as it contains essential fatty acids, minerals, vitamins and digestible energy (Tacon, 1993). With the growing aquaculture, the demand for fish meal and fish oil has been increased and eventually resulted in increased cost of FM and FO (FAO, 2011). Although the fish meal is the primary protein source (Li et al., 2009), the price of fish feed accounts for 40 to 60 % of the total aquaculture production. Therefore, in aqua farming production costs can be increased due to the increase in the price of fish meal (Hardy, 2010; Elnwishy et al., 2012). To enhance the production of the industry of aquaculture fish feed should be replaced with alternative sources of protein to get better health and growth of fish (Tacon, 2003). Insects are the good and cheapest source of protein. Insects are being used for both human consumption and in the feed of animals (FAO, 2011). With a high rate of growth and ease in management (Van Huis, 2013), the insects can be produced in farms and as regional mass production (Hardouin and Mahoux, 2003). Different insects are being used in fish feed including blowfly larvae which are biologically viable, highly nutritive and

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can be easily reared (Ng et al., 2001). This present study was planned to evaluate the effect of insects feed on Tilapia and to find the palatability of blowfly larvae as a protein source along with the commercially available conventional feed ingredients in the laboratory and its implication on an industrial scale. The research aimed to formulate the cheap feed which can promote the growth and health of fish and develop a sustainable fish culture for local farming.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Production of Maggots:

A temporary maggotry was made in a laboratory consisting of 3 plastic buckets. Each bucket was supplied with plant manure at the bottom and a second smaller bucket with poultry meat waste. The collecting pipe was attached to a smaller bucket and the second end was attached to a smaller bucket and collecting box. After one week of placement, it was checked for larvae collection. 8-10 mm long maggots were collected by handpicking and after two weeks, the rotten poultry waste was placed in a bucket full of water. The maggots at the surface of the water were collected and dried at 70 °c in an incubator for 3 hours. After that, they were grounded in mortar and pestle. This grounded material was then used for feed formulation.

Formulation of Fish Feed:

Maggots were produced in maggotry. Wheat bran, Rice polish and yellow corn and premixes were purchased from the local market. Three diets were formulated by using ingredients and grounded maggots. Before adding mag meal, all the dry components, including wheat bran, Rice polish and yellow corn, were equally weighed. They were mixed thoroughly with oil in a bowl. To make it stiff water was added and through a hand pelleting machine, the mixture was pressed to obtain pellets. The feeds were stored at 20 °C. All feeds were separately packed in airtight plastic boxes and labelled. Three groups were made, Group I (diet with 40% insects feed), Group II (diet with 20% insects feed) and Group III (Control Group having no maggot meal) (Table.1).

Analysis of Protein % in Fish Diet and Feces:

Feces samples were collected from every tank by using siphoning pipes at the end of the experiment. After collection, each sample of feces was kept in plastic vials and stored at - 20 °C. To estimate the percentage of crude protein in feed and feces, samples were analyzed by the Kjeldhal method (Helrich, 1990).

Parameters for Growth performance:

The growth performance parameters like body weight gain, FCR, Survival rate and feed utilization was calculated by using the formulas (Sevier et al., 2000)

Statistical analysis:

The obtained data were subjected to statistical analysis by applying one way ANOVA to estimate the effect of the dietary protein on the growth rate of fish.

RESULTS

Water Quality Parameters

Water quality parameters like pH, Temperature, Alkalinity, Hardness and Dissolved Oxygen were maintained at optimum ranges. Range and averages of water quality parameters during the experiment are given in table 2.

Growth performance parameters

Fish consumed all feed actively and the progressive increase was observed in the growth of fingerlings. The values of FCR, SGR, feed intake and weight gain was given in table 3. An average weight gain in Diet (40%) was 1.58 g. Weight gain in Diet 2 (20%) was 6.7 g. While weight gain of Diet (control group) was 2.83 g. Fish feed that feeds on a 20% diet has better weight gain than diet 40% and control group. Analysis of variance showed significant weight gain ($p=0.000$) in all tanks on a weekly basis.

Highest SGR was observed in fish fed on 20% feed than in 40% and 0% feed. It showed that fish fed on 20% diet and 0% fish feed exhibited better SGR than fish fed on 40% fish diets. The highest survival rate during the whole experiment was observed in fish fed on 40% mag meal which was 81.25% and then in 20% diet 73.3%. The lowest survival rate was observed in the control group at 53.3%. Survival rate described the mortality rate of fish that fish are actively consumed by fish and the sustainability of fish (Table 3).

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Averages of feed intake of experimental diets were mentioned in Table 14 that was given to fish on a daily basis. 30.49, 60.82 and 82.28 feed intake was observed in 40%, 20% and 0% maggot diets. FCR is one of the valuable and powerful tools for the fish farmer. It is the amount of feed that is necessary to grow the weight of fish up to 1 kg. 40% and 20% mag meal diets show the lowest (best) FCR as compared to those that fed on the control diet. FCR for 40% and 20 % diets were 1.92 and 0.90 indicates the best utilization of feed by fish.

The percentage of crude protein in experimental feed and feces (Table. 4) was determined by the Kjeldhal method (Helrich, 1990). There was a high percentage of protein in feces of control group than groups fed with insect diet. It showed a significant decrease in the digestibility and consumption of a diet rich in soya bean. However, feed with 40% of insect meal showed more digestibility as compared to feed with 20% insect meal because it showed less protein content percentage in feces. It showed that protein was actively consumed by fish fed on a 40% mag meal diet. Results showed an excellent overall growth performance by 40% and 20% insect feed diet.

DISCUSSION

The present study was designed to find out the potential of Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* to consume insects as a part of the food. It is one of the most important fish in many parts of the world as a food (Pullin, 1997). To cope with the expenses related to conventional fish meal, many scientists are searching for an alternative source of fish meal that has the same effect as like fish meal. Hence, insects are being used as a part of food in fish farming, poultry and pig (Griffin et al., 1994). Experimental diets including maggot meal, can successfully replace the entire fishmeal portion of the fish diet (Ali et al., 2015).

In the present study blow, fly larvae were used as insect meals in formulated feed for Tilapia. The larvae of blowflies grow on the waste of animals and provide a great source of protein for fish (Ng et al., 2001). Maggots of *Chrysoma megacephala* provide a total content of protein (52 %) as compared to maggots of house fly (39%) as well as vitamin B complex, trace elements and phosphorous (Silva et al., 2010).

The environmental factors, throughout the experiment, were kept at optimum ranges. An average value of 7.18 to 7.25 for pH and 5-6.7 mg/l for dissolved oxygen in all tanks efficiently supported the feed utilization efficiency (Balarin and Hatton, 1979). The result of conducting experiments showed that all experimental feed was actively consumed by fish. Uses of different experimental diet ingredients in feed have reduced the effect of some anti-nutrients factors, thus enhancing the overall health of fish and reduced mortality rate (Bascnar, 2007).

The result from the current study is very similar to the findings report by other authors with different quantities or levels of protein in their diet. Abdel-Tawwab et al., 2010 reported the best growth performance in a 45 % protein diet as like our study. Similar results were reported by other authors for different types of diets for tilapia. The difference might be due to different types of diets used as a source of protein. The feed conversion ratio is the most important and valuable parameter to determine how much feed is utilized to get the desired output. It allows for an estimate of the feed that will be required in the growing cycle. Lower FCR values below 1 indicate the most efficient utilization of food and improved growth performance (Sitko et al., 2011). Low (best) values of 0.92 and 0.91 FCR were recorded in 40% and 20% feed which indicates that the maggot meal diet has promoted the growth as like best (low) FCR were reported in high protein diet. Ali et al., 2015 reported that fish fed on maggot diets showed the best (lowest) FCR compared to those fed on commercial diets like the current study. Ahmad et al., 2004 also have the best FCR for tilapia fry was obtained from 35% and 45% protein diets with an insignificant difference. Sing et al., 2014 observed that fish fed on the 100% magmeal diet also showed the best (lowest) FCR (1.34). Abdel-Tawwab et al., 2010 had studied the optimum FCR was obtained when fry tilapia were fed the 45%-CP diet.

On the other hand, higher FCR was reported by Ali et al., 2015, in a control diet which is similar to our findings. It means that the feed utilization efficiency of the control diet was less as compared to the maggot diet. 40% and 20% maggot diet have better performance than control diet and also produced an increase in weight and length. Proteins promote appropriate growth and improve the health of fish, hence this is the most important nutrient that should be included in fish feed (Ogunji and Wirth, 2000). The present study results indicated higher assimilation and consumption of protein given in experimental diets. In comparison with works done by others, the

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findings from the present study agree with results on SGR reported by Ahmad et al., 2004, Nasir, 2013 and Abdel-Tawwab et al., 2010. They all have higher SGR in high dietary protein levels. The overall SGR value of the fish in Treatment I was high (2.25) (Table 14) as the percentage of the crude protein in the diet was the highest. This value increased to 9.57 (Treatment II) and to 4.40 (Treatments III) while the crude protein in the fish diet was lower. A slight decrease in SGR value at protein levels above the optimum causes a reduction in dietary energy offered for the growth since more energy is needed to control absorbed amino acids (Jauncey, 1982). Feed utilization was significantly affected by protein level and fish weight but not their interaction. Higher values of SGR and lower values of FCR revealed better growth performance in fingerlings of Tilapia (Khattab et al., 2000). Dietary protein is necessary for fish feeding (Jauncey and Ross, 1982) and a sufficient quantity of dietary protein is required by fish to gain rapid growth. The results from the present investigation indicated that the percentage range of dietary protein from 2.81 % to 12.75 % is beneficial for the fingerlings of Tilapia to gain 0.40 to 0.51 g/day. Optimum dietary protein levels ranged from 27 to 37% in Nile Tilapia in juvenile stages which gradually decreases as the fish grows (Yamamoto et al., 2000). In the present study, the decrease of crude protein in feces of Nile tilapia reflected the increased protein concentration in the body. This can be associated with increased absorption of protein from the maggotry diet. This reflects that the maggot diet has been consumed by fish which promoted the growth of fish (Yamamoto et al., 2000). The results of this study concluded that maggot meals could be successfully used in the diet of fish due to the observed differences in growth performance. It also enhanced the growth rate of fish and improved their health as reported earlier (Ogunji et al., 2006).

CONCLUSION

The present study concludes that insect meal is a great replacement for other expensive alternatives as it promotes the digestibility and utilization of protein and other nutrients at a greater level. Furthermore, it provides a cheaper source of protein not only for fish but for other farmed animals as a part of the diet. The study indicates that blowfly larvae can be the best source of insect protein along with other insects that are commercially available. However, it opens further needs of research in experimenting with different insect based diets with different formulations to attain much better results.

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Table 1: Feed Formula/ Treatments of the Experimental Diet

Ingredients	Control Group	Treatment 1	Treatment 2
Insect Feed	0 %	20 %	40 %
Soya bean	40 %	20 %s	10 %
Wheat bran	20 %	20 %	20 %
Rice polish	20 %	20 %	20 %
Yellow corn	20 %	20 %	10 %
Premixes	20 %	20 %	20 %
Fats	20 %	20	20 %

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Table 2: Physical and Chemical parameters of water

Items	pH	Temperature	Total Hardness	D.O	Alkalinity
Ranged	7.18:7.25	28: 30 °c	50-150 ppm	5.7- 6.0	80 – 180 ppm
Averages	7.8± 0.14	25.5 ±2.12	45 ±115	7	75.7 ±175.5

Table 3: Growth performance of *Oreochromis niloticus* in 40 %, 20 % and control group

Diet	(Tank 1) 40 %	Tank 2 (20) %	Tank 3 Control group
Weight gain	1.58	6.7	2.83
SGR %	2.25 %	9.57 %	4.04 %
FI	30.49	60.82	82.28
FCR	0.92	0.90	2.25
Survival %	81.25	73.3 %	53.3 %

Table 4: Percentage of crude protein in fish Diet and feces

Percentage of Protein	Fish Diet			Fish Feces		
	40 %	20 %	Control	40 %	20 %	Control
	2.81 %	5.18 %	12.75 %	0.0687 %	0.19375 %	0.28125 %

Highlights:

1. The results clearly indicated that use of insects in the fish diet is cost effective.
2. It promotes growth with higher usage of protein as compared to other conventional feeds.
3. Blowfly larvae were evidenced as the best substitute for expensive feed components for fish.